

COMMUNICATIVE STRATEGIES OF AMERICAN TWIPLOMACY

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Abstract

The article studies the linguopragmatic peculiarities and communicative strategies of one of the genres of digital diplomatic discourse – Twiplomacy. Twiplomacy is a form of digital diplomacy conducted by diplomats and heads of state using social media platform X (formerly Twitter).

The article shows that Twitter messages of diplomatic institutions and diplomats use a range of diplomatic strategies that serve to influence target audience and build a positive image. The article describes and classifies communicative strategies that diplomats and politicians resort to in social network called Twitter into informative, judgmental and argumentative. Moreover, the article finds that the participants of Twiplomacy widely employ a range of tactics within the judgmental strategy: tactics of positive representation, defamation, implied or explicit negative representation, etc.

The study also distinguishes institutional and personal diplomatic discourse arguing that those two discourses pursue different communicative goals and, therefore, resort to different communicative strategies. Institutional discourse refers to communication of diplomatic departments or ministries with the public, while personal discourse is employed by individual diplomats and politicians.

Keywords: digital diplomacy, Twiplomacy, communicative strategy, institutional discourse, personalized discourse.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern research in the field of new types of discourse that have emerged as a result of the development of information technologies determines genuine interest in the study of the discourse of digital diplomacy as a new communicative practice that has appeared with the development of new information technologies. And the study of linguopragmatic features of a new type of discourse corresponds to modern trends in pragmalinguistics in general and studies of speech manipulation in particular. Digital diplomacy, as an independent genre of diplomatic discourse, uses the communicative space of the Internet to realize foreign policy interests, which is one of the determining factors in the characteristics of communication within the new discourse.

Diplomacy has evolved throughout its history, adapting to changes in state policies, leaders, and the emergence of new conflicts and alliances. For a long time, diplomatic discourse was closed and accessible only to a limited circle of people. Informing the wider population occurred through the media, where messages were often of little substance. Today, diplomatic discourse is becoming more open, and the informational component of diplomats' activities is strengthening due to the active introduction of information technologies, among which social networks have already occupied their specific niche. Digital social media have become a new way to reach a wider audience. The current level of development of diplomatic practice on the Internet using IT technologies allows us to talk about the formation of a discourse of digital diplomacy as a new form of diplomatic discourse that contributes to the formation and development of dynamic communicative practice at the present stage of world development. Moreover, Twitter has become so popular in the practice of digital diplomacy that international relations experts identify Twiplomacy as a new way of social network diplomacy [6].

The purpose of this article is to analyze the specifics of the use of discursive strategies in digital diplomacy within one of the social platforms used: Twitter. To achieve this goal, we analyzed the Twitter accounts of US President Joe Biden [4], former US President Donald Trump [3], US Secretary of State Antony Blinken [2] and the US State Department [1] as the main American diplomatic institution.

2. COMMUNICATIVE STRATEGIES

Based on the typology of speech strategies by G. P. Grice [5], O. S. Issers [7], as well as the scientific conclusions of N.V. Novikov [8] and based on the analysis of the factual material, we identified the following main types of communicative strategies in the English text of diplomacy, such as an informative strategy, an judgmental and an argumentative strategy.

2.1 Informative strategy

The goal of the informative strategy is neutral, non-judgmental coverage of certain events that correspond to the topic of the informative source. As a rule, such texts represent a notification about some event; they are more typical for the accounts of diplomatic departments, that is, for the institutional discourse of digital diplomacy:

In "The Week at State," we announced a new partnership with the @Smithsonian, @VP Harris chaired a National Space Council meeting, and @SecBlinken met with reporters for an end of the year press conference. [1]

Such texts do not contain value judgments and do not appeal to any peculiarities of perception among potential recipients, i.e. represent an informational diplomatic message for the media and mass audience of the information resource.

2.2 Judgmental strategy

Fundamentally different from the informative strategy is the judgmental strategy. The purpose of this strategy is to form a certain perception by the addressee of the object of the statement. The image can be both positive and negative, which is reflected in the applied tactics of the judgmental strategy. The analysis showed that this strategy is implemented by the following tactics:

- the tactics of positive representation appeal to positively charged meanings in the minds of recipients, based, as a rule, on their value guidelines [9]:

This year @SecBlinken traveled more than 250,000 miles to support international relations and work toward a more peaceful and prosperous world. Here's a collection of some of the most memorable moments.[1]

It is worth noting that such messages contain an emotional connotation, as indicated by emotive vocabulary. In personalized diplomatic discourse, the tactics of positive representation and self-presentation are often directly linked to the marketing of the diplomat's personality. For example, a post from US President Joe Biden:

The Inflation Reduction Act is going to lower costs, save lives for people who forgo drugs because they can't afford them, and give folks a little more breathing room. This is Bidenomics is all about. [3]

In addition to highlighting his philanthropic activities, the message highlights the American president's support for national security activities. Positive self-presentation is often associated with a strategy of empathy (sympathy) and complementary discourse, which solves two problems at once: a positive

representation of the addressee and a positive self-presentation.

- defamation tactics are responsible for a negative representation of the object of the statement. This tactic manifests itself primarily in personalized discourse, since in the institutional discourse of diplomatic departments open criticism is simply inappropriate. For example, the following message from Donald Trump, where he resorts to defamation tactics to discredit his political rival:

Joe Biden got tongue tied over the weekend when he was unable to properly deliver a very simple line about his decision to run for President. Get used to it, another low I.Q. individual! [3]

Using the nomination low I.Q. in the text. individual (a person with a low I.Q.), Donald Trump creates a negative image of another politician among the global Internet public, characterizing him in this way.

However, the most widespread in digital diplomacy has become an implicit or explicit appeal to value orientations that are negative for a particular culture. One of the global human and political values is equality, and any kind of discrimination causes rejection among the audience. Therefore, the use of related terminology in digital diplomacy is employed to discredit political opponents. For example, this technique is used in the following message from US Secretary of State Antony Blinken:

The United States expresses grave concern regarding reports the Burmese military has detained multiple civilian government and civil society leaders. The military must reverse these actions immediately. [2]

2.3 Argumentation strategy

Argumentation strategies are traditional for diplomatic practice and were used long before the introduction of information technology into diplomatic discourse. Such strategies involve the use of argumentative means: citations, eyewitness accounts, reliable sources of information, digital evidence. The verbalization of such techniques is expressed in linguistic strategies - the use of linguistic means of a rational and emotional nature: the choice of words, phrases, metaphors, epithets.

Real average hourly earnings rose 1.9% during the past 12 months, well exceeding the 0.4% pace during the year-earlier period. Real wages for American families are soaring. #CPI #BLSdata [1]

In this example, the addressee points to the growth of citizens' incomes, supporting this with specific figures. Moreover, the message contains an indication of the source of this information. The hashtag #BLSdata refers to the US Bureau of Labor Statistics, which provided the wage data.

As the analysis showed, in digital diplomacy, argumentation strategies are used extremely rarely, despite the obvious advantages of reasoned communicative influence. The most common strategies of digital diplomatic discourse are informative strategies (characteristic of institutional discourse) and judgmental strategies (for personalized discourse).

Thus, our analysis revealed a number of main strategies used in the discourse of digital diplomacy. Addressees of this discourse resort to informative, judgmental (through positive representation or defamation) and argumentative strategies on the social network Twitter. In general, the above strategies do not imply isolation within the text of an English-language IR and, as a rule, are combined, creating a more significant communicative-pragmatic effect. In conclusion, it should be noted that, taking into account the distinctive parameters of communication on social networks, including Twitter, the study of the linguistic features of various genres of English-language digital diplomacy is of undoubted scientific interest.

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